

OPTIMIZATION OF APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATIONS AFTER FISTULIZING OPERATIONS IN CHILDREN WITH PRIMARY CONGENITAL GLAUCOMA

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Abstract. *The main treatment for congenital glaucoma is surgery to achieve target IOP without the use of drugs [1.5]. Early complications include small anterior chamber syndrome, hyphema, ciliochoroidal detachment, excessive hypotony and hypertension. The probability of these complications is quite high: according to some data, it can reach 50%, which indicates the relevance of this problem [7.4]. Aims and objectives are to study early postoperative complications in children with primary congenital glaucoma and methods of their correction after antiglaucomatous surgery by combined technique with simultaneous influence on 3 outflow pathways. 151 children (270 eyes) who underwent antiglaucomatous surgery by the combined method and early postoperative complications were examined. The analysis of the results of antiglaucomatous operation in the early postoperative period showed that on the first day the total number of patients was 62.6%. On the third day the total number of patients with complications increased up to 67,4%. Of these, the largest number of patients were those with marked hypotonia - 33.3%, hyphema - 10.0% and ocular hypertension - 6.7%. After conservative treatment, on the seventh day, the total number of complications decreased to 10%. Thus, after conservative treatment, the number of complications in the early postoperative period decreased by 52.6%. There was no need for repeated surgical intervention in these patients. Patients were discharged home under the supervision of an ophthalmologist at their place of residence.*

Keywords: *primary congenital glaucoma, anti-glaucomatous surgery, early postoperative complications.*

Relevance. Glaucoma has taken the first place in the structure of blindness and primary visual disability. Clinical symptoms are photophobia, lacrimation, blepharospasm, increase in the size of the eyeball, oedema and increase in the size of the cornea, excavation of the RPE [4,5,10,11,17].

The basis of the pathomechanism of primary congenital glaucoma is dysgenesis of the anterior chamber angle and increased intraocular pressure.

Therefore, the main principle of glaucoma treatment is to systematically lower IOP to a safe level.

Since goniodysgenesis is the main pathogenetic factor of congenital glaucoma, fistulising surgeries for glaucoma are most often used by ophthalmic surgeons and are the 'gold standard' of congenital glaucoma surgery. But, despite its effectiveness, in the postoperative period they are accompanied by serious complications such as: ciliochoroidal detachment, uveitis, haemorrhagic complications, etc. [4,5,17,18].

According to different authors, the incidence of postoperative ciliochoroidal detachment (PCD) varies widely - from 0.9 to 90% [Alekseev V.N., 1976; Krasnov M.M., 1980; Babushkin A.E., 1992]. The development of CCHO in the early postoperative period can be complicated by sluggish uveitis, hypotonic maculopathy, secondary glaucoma due to pupil seclusion and

contraction of the anterior chamber angle, increase in glaucomatous keratopathy, etc. [1,3,4,7,14,15,16].

Despite the in-depth study of this nosology in the analysed literature, there are no clear criteria for the choice of one or another method of treatment of early postoperative complications, proposed by the authors, for any one particular form of complication. At the same time, there is a clear need to develop a pathogenetically justified method of treatment taking into account anatomical features in the most complex forms of primary congenital glaucoma.

Objective of the study. To study early postoperative complications in children with primary congenital glaucoma and methods of their correction after antiglaucoma surgery by combined method with one-stage effect on 3 outflow pathways.

Material and Methods. From 2020 to 2023, we operated on 151 children (270 eyes) aged from 20 days to 3 years on the basis of the eye department of the clinic of the Tashkent Paediatric Medical Institute. Children with secondary, combined glaucoma and children with systemic diseases were not included in the group. All children were hospitalised as an emergency. After thorough preparation, all patients underwent antiglaucomatous surgery. Of the examined children, boys accounted for 54% (81) and girls - for 46% (70).

All children underwent a comprehensive general clinical and ophthalmological examination, including visometry, biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, gonioscopy, echobiometry, and tonometry. Tonometry was performed according to the Maklakov method 3-5 minutes after induction of anaesthesia. Dimedrol 1% and atropine sulfate 0.1% were used for premedication; a combination of sibazon 0.5%, sodium oxybutyrate (GHB) 40% and fentanyl 0.005% was used for induction. All children underwent antiglaucomatous surgery using a combined method developed at our department, which includes a one-stage effect on the outflow pathways in 3 directions: Burian sinusotrabeculotomy into the scleral sinus, cyclodialysis-cyclorejection with autoscleral pedicle into the suprachoroidal space, basal iridectomy with sclerectomy under the scleral flap into the episcleral venous system (Patent for invention 'Method of surgical treatment of congenital glaucoma' No. IAP 04890 dated 12. 05.2014).

Results and Discussion. The material was collected in the period from 2016 to 2023, for the period from 2016 to 2019, a retrospective analysis of case histories of patients with primary congenital glaucoma (PVG) hospitalised in the eye department of the TashPMI clinic was conducted. A prospective analysis of examination and surgical treatment of patients with PVG was conducted from 2020 to 2023.

When making the diagnosis, we used the ICD-10 classification and the classification of A.P. Nesterov and E.A. Egorov (2001). For detailed description of the pathological process in congenital glaucoma we used the classification of N.A. Kachan and T.K. Toikuliev (2004).

The distribution of eyes by stages of the disease showed that the initial stage occurred in 36 (13.3%), developed - 53 (19.6%), far advanced - 149 (55.2%), and terminal - 32 (11.9%) eyes, respectively. All patients underwent surgical intervention according to our proposed method. Complications were observed in the postoperative period. The most frequent complications in the early postoperative period (up to 7 days) included CCHO, hyphema, IOP elevation, shallow anterior chamber syndrome and hypotension.

On the first day after surgery, hypotony - (-) 0.5 - 1.0 and minor chorioideal oedema were diagnosed in 122 (45.2%) eyes with a typical clinical picture for such a complication. These patients were prescribed Atropine sulphate instillations in age-appropriate doses 2 times a day. 47 (17.4%) eyes showed an increase of intraocular pressure up to (+)1.0. The probable cause of IOP increase after the operation was viscoelastic and the presence of sterile air introduced into the

anterior chamber for its resorption at the final stage of the operation. As it was resorbed, IOP was restored to the planned level. Normal intraocular pressure was detected in 101 eyes (37.4%).

On the third day in the postoperative period, high pressure persisted in 18 (6.7%) eyes. In 88 (32.6%) eyes intraocular pressure was within the normal range and in 74 (27.4%) there was a decrease to (-)0.5. In 90 (33.3%) eyes hypotony (-)1.0 was detected and on B-scan there was marked chorioideal oedema. In this connection they were prescribed conservative treatment (Atropine sulphate eye drops in age doses 2 times a day, Caffeine-benzoate sodium 3% instillation into conjunctival sac 4-5 times a day). On the 5th day, pronounced hypotony greater than (-) 1.0 and detachment of CSF was observed in 70 (25.9%). These patients were prescribed Caffeine-benzoate sodium 3% instillation into the conjunctival sac 4-5 times a day, Dexamethasone 0.4% lymphotropically 0.5ml once a day and pressure dressing once a day.

On the seventh day in the postoperative period, ophthalmic hypertension persisted in 9 (3.3%) eyes, in this regard, IOP lowering drugs were recommended: Arutimol eye drops 0.25% 2 times a day or VisiPres 2% eye drops 2 times a day. In 18 (6.67%) eyes hypotonia was pronounced and detachment of the CSF was observed. It developed against the background of small anterior chamber syndrome and unsuccessful conservative treatment. It was recommended to continue conservative treatment in hospital (Dexamethasone instillations 2 drops 6 times a day and continue Dexamethasone lymphotropically). After conservative treatment IOP normalised and the patients were discharged home under the supervision of an ophthalmologist at the place of residence.

Thus, the total number of patients with CCHO was 25.97% on the fifth day after surgery, these figures decreased to 6.57% on the seventh day after conservative treatment. The obtained data coincide with the data of the literature that early complications include small anterior chamber syndrome and CCHO. The probability of these complications is quite high: according to some data, it can reach 50% [13,14].

Any manifestation of blood in the anterior chamber from the formations to the level was considered as hyphema. A total of 42 eyes (15.57%) had such cases on the first day, on the third day hyphema persisted in 27 (10.0%) eyes, on the seventh day hyphema with hypotony was observed in 17 (6.59%) eyes. These patients were prescribed Emoprox 1% eye drops 2 drops 2 times a day. After the treatment the pressure normalised, hyphema resolved and all patients were discharged home under the supervision of an ophthalmologist at the place of residence

Conclusion. The analysis of the structure of early postoperative complications after antiglaucomatous surgery by combined method with one-stage effect on 3 outflow pathways showed that on the first day the total number of patients with complications was 62.6%. On the third day the total number of patients with complications increased to 67.4%. Of these, the largest number of patients were those with pronounced hypotonia 33.3%, hyphema -10.0% and ophthalmic hypertension - 6.7%. After conservative treatment on the seventh day, the total number of complications decreased by 52.6% to 10%. All patients were discharged home under the supervision of an ophthalmologist at the place of residence.

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